

‘Play’ as an Epistemological Framework for Studying the Youth and the Smartphone Screen

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Abstract: *This essay will make an attempt to read theoretical, conceptual work and fieldwork observations which have pointed towards the possibility of developing a ‘play’ as an epistemological framework which can best ensconce the research question of this essay – how to study the youth and their experiences with the smartphone screen which cannot be neatly categorized as media use and/or consumption? This is an important concern as the goals of Viksit Bharat include the mobilization of the youth in realizing the developmental goals of the country. The smartphone screen, and what the youth do with it, hence becomes a crucial element to be studied and understood. The new, handheld digital screens in particular can be seen as the site of emerging consumption practices and human interaction with the smartphone screen can be located in the discursive field of automation, mobility and sensorial experiences. The ontological and epistemological problem of categorizing media practices which cannot be neatly labelled as use or consumption have led to exploration of finding new frameworks, models and tools of examining contemporary media experiences. This paper will argue that an epistemological framework that factors in ‘playful’ nature of media consumption and use, can at least partially explain the use of new media by the youth, especially the smartphone screen, in producing ideas around culture and identity.*

Introduction

The core ontological argument in the issue of technology and culture has had an enduring and looming presence in media and cultural studies. It heavily relies on dualism which limits and underpins all discussion in new media debates as well. It sways from two extremes of technological determinism and human agency. It is either posited as technology *causing* changes in cultures or technology as an *effect* of on-going changes in cultures. In other words it is a recurrent problem of technological cultures, and it emerges when we revisit the debates between Raymond Williams and Marshall McLuhan. Both these scholars differed in how they mapped and navigated the field of technology and culture. Evidently, the former position invests all power and agentic capacity to technology, and the latter insists on the power and agency of humans in culture and society. While both are deterministic in their boundaries, Williams’ ideas of society, culture and technology continue to pre-dominantly hold sway in the field of this study. Hence the debates on cultural changes have been eclipsed by studying cultural phenomena by focusing on human agencies and capacities only. There has been a strong resistance to reduce any medium to the technology or to centrally place the technology of that medium as a focus of study. For Williams (30) the rationale behind the invention of a technology is significant. He argues that every technology is geared towards aiding existing human practices or possible future needs and uses. In other words the notion of practice as well as human intentionality and action are key to examining any technology in society. Further for him technologies build on already existing practices and needs of social groups, emerging and situated within a complex interplay of economic, social and cultural conditions, and hence this process is entirely sociological (130). Here I would like to argue that we must examine the

limits of this position which is almost always culturalist, as even Williams (135) himself hinted at, and ironically even seemed to share McLuhan's position when discussing the development of new communication televisual technologies in the 1970s that would lead to the emergence of institutions that would differ from either purely 'public service' or 'commercial' broadcasting and perhaps transform broadcasting itself.

There has now been a renewed interest in the work of Marshall McLuhan, and in what can be seen as a clash of ideas and discourses in the study of technology and culture. For McLuhan, any technology ushered cultural and social shifts in society, shaping and re-shaping the relationships between them. Subsequently for him technologies and media are complex social actors and in essence, every new technology is considered capable of producing social and cultural change. Among many of his ideas, a few significant ones include his concept of 'remediation' (that the content of any particular medium is in fact another medium), second that all technologies and media are essentially an extension of the human body and senses, and third that 'the medium is the message' or in other words the characteristics of the medium are equally if not more important to understand and analyse than the content of that medium (15-16). What McLuhan provides are non-linear and playful ways of thinking about new media. Bolter and Grusin (76) for instance have built upon McLuhan's work to speak about remediation or the power of every medium to remediate, which is appropriating the form and techniques of previous media forms. Further they argue that it is important to recognize what McLuhan calls the media as "extensions of the human sensorium" and in that sense there is essentially no distinction between a medium and technology. This conflation also points to the extension of human senses of light, touch, hearing and sight which changes our sensory experiences, and is significant culturally. For McLuhan such extensions of the body and their interaction with the body's sensorium affectively impacts minds, cultures and society as, "sense ratios change when any sense or bodily or mental function is externalised in technological form" (64). Hence consequently for him the message of any medium or technology in question is the transformation and change that it augurs in lives. This is not to suggest that the actual content of the medium is immaterial, but it helps focus attention to how media technologies contribute towards shaping sociality. Additionally this framework also emphasizes on the aesthetic properties of technologies, devices and media as they mediate experiences and engage with senses in various ways. In this sense, the media transforms the relationship of the body and the sensorium with the environment it is located in. This then shows the value of mapping the interaction between human and non-human agency, as technology and its effects cannot be entirely reduced to its social uses.¹

In identifying how technologies are fast going out of human control, Eriksen (272-273) cautions against the speed of these technological developments which also characterize how they impact the speed of human actions as well. In a specific discussion on dissemination of information, he problematizes the pace of these technologies and argues that it can result in casualties of context and credibility by placing an accent on the speed at which the tasks are accomplished rather than how effectively and truly they create and deliver meaning. Ultimately, for him, the dangers of technologies are far greater and the unintended consequences far more severe than the conveniences they offer to humans, and hence requires our reflection on this creation of a new reality.

In a different light, remarking on the interactive nature of communication technologies, Barry (163-164) sees immense potential in their ability to make citizens active participants in a democracy. For him, the interactivity of new media technologies encourages citizen participation, thereby allowing agentic action in the fields of education, media and governance. Through a few case studies he makes an argument for acknowledging the contribution of these technologies that treat citizens as active participants and offers them choice and agency. Slightly differently, but arguing towards the same end, Barber (200-201) considers new media technologies as offering access to information and knowledge and is optimistic of its democratic possibilities. However, he does warn against its appropriation by those in power or the governments to control and discipline citizens. For him the way out would be to build stronger political institutions and have collective will to use these technologies to promote knowledge, diversity and participation.

There is also emerging work, such as that of Latour's (54-62) Actor Network Theory, which urges us to revisit and rethink the culture/technology debate and provide new accounts of cultural phenomena. Technology then is not occasional or fleeting, it does and can have capacities for non-human agency, and is at the core of any analysis of culture. This requires a kind of dialogue between all the players of cultural production because technologies produce certain kind of affordances which allow for certain cultural possibilities. Latour very carefully rearranges the source of agency from humans alone to ascribing even technology with agentic capacities in their interaction and experience with each other.

Verbeek (36) also discusses if technologies allow humans to "exist as themselves" as technologies lead to legitimate existential questions. Borrowing from Jasper (26) he calls these moments "boundary situations" where technologies change human life, but also make it possible for humans to be more human. He in fact goes on to argue that the problem of choice is not that of limiting, but plenty, and that technology facilitates too many choices for humans. Hence for him the issue is what possibilities does technology give rise to eventually.

From the above discussion on technology and culture, perhaps studying how we *use* technology is limiting and focussing instead on how it alters human interaction, society and cultures would be a fruitful approach, keeping in mind the affordances and limitations it produces, for technology becomes the very medium we are inhabiting. Hence foreclosing the possibility that technology cannot produce cultural changes would be entirely limiting. The affective smartphone screen extends the human sensorium, to remediate experiences and engage human senses in newer ways. In many ways as McLuhan has suggested, technologies (and the screen here) self-extends, specifically in the contemporary context of an increasingly complex technological culture.

Playful turn in Media Studies

The concept of play then is emerging as a useful way to account for new modes of consumption, production, distribution, reception, engagement and re-use. A basic way to define play would be, "free movement within a more rigid structure" (Salen and Zimmerman 304) where play also has the possibility of overwhelming the larger structure. This definition accounts for two things, a) providing a useful concept to engage with contemporary media practices, and b) highlighting the dynamism of the interplay between agentic action (human) and controlling structures (human and non-human technology) in media experiences. Play is

emerging as an everyday mode of living digital lives. Media technologies have increasingly ludic interfaces (Fuchs 32) and users now possess great amounts of ludic literacy (Zagal 267) or gaming literacy (Zimmerman 55). One of the primary tensions that operate here then are how playful media has the possibilities of facilitating agentic action, but also stands the risk of being co-opted or controlled by a larger structure, as will be argued in subsequent chapters.

McLuhan (89) in discussing games as an extension of social man, considered that they belonged to the sphere of media, as extensions of man's senses and physical body. Fiske (04) also addressed this playfulness that emerges in the interaction between a medium and the user, suggesting that every text has the element of 'play' in it as well as a form of play which enables users to play with the text and its interpretations, oscillating between freedom and control. He foregrounds the concept of pleasure in media use, without dismissing it as mindless consumption, going on to suggest that there is pleasure in breaking the rules as well. Other scholars have also previously established the link between media and play in various ways, such as Stephenson, Silverstone, Raessens, Buckland, Fuchs et al and Frissen et al.

Raessens for instance has spoken of how *ludic* became a popular term in 1960s to refer to playfulness and fun objects, drawing on how computer and video games were characterised as such (45). However he also argued that play is not only limited to leisure but can be invoked in other contexts such as that of education, politics and warfare or even everyday communication such as that via mobile phones. He calls this the 'ludification of culture' that involves game-like elements in non-game contexts (95). He also draws on the general process of *gamification*, a term put forward and popularised by Nick Pelling in 2002.² He is often credited with coining the term gamification, though it had existed earlier in the form of loyalty programs and incentive initiatives by companies. Pelling was tasked with making ATM machines more interactive and game-like. Subsequently he worked on various information communication technologies to make them more interactive or gamified devices. He has argued that Apple devices are primarily premised on the idea of gamification, above everything else, by making them automated and easy-to-use interactive devices (34).

Deterding et al also traced the evolution of the concept of gamification to the digital media industry, and especially video game design to be specific. However, they argue that in the last decade, the term has assumed significance for the use of *gameful* techniques in non-game contexts. They discuss the two prominent ideas present in the concept of gamification, first is the proliferate use of video games in everyday life and second is the increasing trend towards focusing on entertainment and not utility (11). This makes devices and their design more pleasurable, leading to interactivity, longer engagement and loyalty. This they further suggest has seeped into the contexts of other cultural products in a non-game context, to make it a playful use of a service or a commodity.

Raessens 2006 subsequently advances the claim that the concept of play can be used epistemologically as a lens and tool to understand contemporary media culture, by calling it a 'ludic turn in media theory' (100). He discusses that the concept of play has only recently entered media research scholarship, due to socio-cultural changes, transformation in media platforms and technology, and new approaches in media studies and education. According to him, specifically in the Western context, but applicable elsewhere as well, different domains of life such

as politics, economics, education, technology etc. are all governed by a set of rules, involving complex game-like moves without an absolute destination (94). The changes in media themselves which have led to experimentation with content and platform, and the use of playful narrative techniques have also bolstered this ludification process, especially in the context of new media, which as I have also argued subsequently, offer for instance, the concept of playing and streaming content. Media audience-users are invited to play with the content they consume and creatively engage with technologies, platforms and devices, making it desirable to probe this playfulness and gamification.

Reflecting on the slow emergence of play studies within media studies scholarship, Raessens speaks of the silos in which game studies have developed, foreclosing any foray by media studies scholars to engage with games as form of media experience (121). It is only recently that scholars are considering how play can be central to researching and understanding media culture (Silverstone, Neitzel and Nohr, and Thimm). Finally, the development of disciplines such as new media have also warranted a study of new media products such as games, from a media studies perspective, and vice versa to facilitate collaborative, contemporary and relevant research.

Undoubtedly, contemporary media culture is imbricated in a close relationship with digital technologies and play. While the concepts of play and game differ in how play refers to a broader category, and includes all game and non-game activities of playful communication, Caillois (62) has introduced terms like competition, mimicry, chance and vertigo as useful concepts to understand the concept of play in general. He in his framework, allows for a certain freedom in moving between rules and structures and accommodating spontaneity in games, though ironically, the freedom aspect of the game emergence only after surrendering to the rules of play in the first place. Raessens (104) however goes forward with Huizinga's concept of play, and argues that media offer various 'affordances' to play – multiple realities, many interpretations, possibilities of pleasure, frustration with rules and limitations. Expanding on the levels of playability, he further posits that first there is a player who surrenders to the rules and lets the game govern, the second are those who game the system, or try and bend the rules, the third are those who deliberately ignore the rules and modify the game, and the last are those who shape the game itself as programmers (105). Another significant point put forward by him relates to media literacy, the simultaneous autonomy of playing but also being governed by rules (technology). He argues that contemporary media systems also require media skills and knowledge to know the rules of play and to have the knowledge to work this mediated world (107). This is similar to what Zimmerman (78) has also called 'gaming literacy' is the larger knowledge of playing by the rules, bending them or adjusting wherever required. Defending the playful turn in media studies without overstating their significance, Raessen further argues that there have been many breaks in quick succession such as the linguistic, material, visual, spatial, cultural and digital turn in media scholarship. In his assessment the current scenario of media as playful objects combines the presence of computer games, playful aspects of media consumption and use, and media literacy of ludification. He elaborates on rules, variabilities, immersion, and pleasures as important aspects of the contemporary digital media experience (110). This is then a useful approach to analyse contemporary screen media culture, specifically in reference to self-tracking, OTT use and dating culture practices.

Interrogating Digital and Mobile Technologies

Echoing Raessens, Glas et al speak of and interrogate the emergence of digital and mobile technologies through the lens of play. They similarly argue that the idea of play is not limited to games, playground and childhood but has entered hitherto non-game like contexts, such as everyday media consumption and use. They further discuss the ontological claim of living in a play world and an epistemological break in developing newer tools to understand every media experience. Since media themselves, and media practices have become more playful, they argue that technologies, practices and approaches need to factor this culture of playfulness. They argue that play offers new ways of understanding media practices, by exploring it in, “dynamic and processual terms: as experimental, as rehearsal, as continual competition, as joking and mischievous, as engaging and participatory, as a type of meta-communication...” (8)

Kucklich and Fellow have also argued that in times to come, digital game studies will contribute to new media studies significantly, since developments in gaming also have an impact on the development of new media landscape in general, and specifically in terms of mode, content, platform and interfaces. They also reveal the apparent reluctance of using ‘play’ as a concept because of its association with childhood and meaningless ‘playing around’ (2). This according to them is slowly changing as the perception of play also continues to shape ideas of youth and youthfulness. Traditionally work and play have existed as different and contained aspects of human life, rarely intermingling or seeping into each other. However, the proliferate use of digital technologies such as the smartphone screen challenge this distinction, with work and play leaking from the strict boundaries, blurring the distinction. This also includes learning the skills and rules to play. They also argue that the pejorative description of play as ‘escapism’ betrays its cultural significance (4). This perhaps has also encouraged media industries to build devices, platforms and interfaces playfully, to ease the transition from work and leisure, making the distinction impossible, and consumption ubiquitous. For instance, online messaging services are increasingly used for work and leisure, online video platforms are used in work contexts and for personal interaction, and social media platforms used for personal and professional achievements. Additionally, online shopping and media consumption is positioned as a game-like activity, inviting users to play content, games and quizzes, using gifts and rewards as tools for immersion, interest and loyalty. They also alert us to not be tempted to use the concepts of game and play without analytical academic rigor or succumbing to the power of the metaphor (5). They stress on the use of the term playability and playfulness, to indicate the affordances, pleasures and restrictions of play in new media context. Playability then is incumbent on three factors: media technology, the text’s characteristics and the audience-user’s media literacy in a kind of digital feedback loop, where all these parts exert control over one another (6). Playfulness on the other hand would refer to an attitude that encourages playability. These concepts of play, they argue, can be useful in understanding the specifics of new media by mapping them together, keeping in mind both the user and the text.

This foregoing discussion highlights the usefulness of using ‘play’ as a framework for examining mediation via the smartphone screen, as it more holistically accounts for new forms of engagement, affective experiences and conditions of mediation for audience-users.

In Lieu of a Conclusion

This preceding discussion has a larger relevance beyond this study and the questions it raises will complicate the study of technological cultures with respect to Viksit Bharat further in multiple ways. For the last few decades, digital media, new media artefacts and information communication technologies in the media have been pursued in many academic disciplines. It is a deeply cultural, social, political and economic phenomenon. Hence it is not surprising that it is being studied for its cultural impact, social changes, political possibilities and commercial flows. The long-standing theoretical traditions of communication and media, psychology, literature, computer science and technology, geography, sociology, political theory among others have studied new media artefacts using existing conceptual frameworks, to accommodate them as-is, in studying medium, representation, content, reception, influences and uses. Survey of the existing dominant paradigms, reveals a case for a theoretical and conceptual reconfiguration and innovation in order to understand the experiences of the conditions of mediation, and account for the ruptures initiated by these new developments in technology. Further, many influential media theories may be inadequate and may not be able to fully account for newer forms and practices of emerging technologies. We might at this point, have to compel ourselves to rethink the relationship between contemporary media theories and practice. This paper has made an attempt to argue that an epistemological framework that factors in the 'playful' nature of media consumption and use, can at least partially explain the use of new media by the youth, especially the smartphone screen, in producing ideas around culture and identity.

Endnotes

1. Many others have referenced McLuhan in their work on cultural discussions on technology and new media in particular, such as Baudrillard (1997) in the 'Implosion of Meaning in the Media' where he argues how the media constitutes the postmodern society, a kind of an independent social force. Extending McLuhan's 'medium is the message', Baudrillard offers that the implosion of media content suggests not just the end of a meaningful message, but the end of the medium itself (p. 102-103). Kroker (1992) expressly uses McLuhan's extension argument further to suggest that technologies create an environment that is composed of 'the externalisation of the human nervous system' (p. 64).
2. Pelling, N., 2011. The (short) prehistory of "gamification"... Funding Startups (& other impossibilities). Available at: <https://nanodome.wordpress.com/2011/08/09/the-short-prehistory-of-gamification/> [Accessed September 16, 2020]

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